

Integration of **Geodetic** and **imAging**
TecHniques for monitoring and
modelling the **Earth's** surface
defo**R**mations and **Seismic** risk

Deliverable 6.2

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

WROCLAW UNIVERSITY
OF ENVIRONMENTAL
AND LIFE SCIENCES

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857612.

Work Package	6. Communication & Dissemination
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable responsible	Innovation & Data Manager (IDM) – Witold Rohm (witold.rohm@upwr.edu.pl)
Number of Pages	16

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Revision history	Date	Details	Editor
1.1	16.03.2020	Content revision	G. Józków (QM)
1.2	21.03.2020	Second draft	W. Rohm (IDM)
1.3	23.03.2020	Revision	K. Kopańczyk (AFM)
1.4	28.03.2020	Revision	N. Pfeifer (WP3)
1.5	30.03.2020	Revision	R. Hanssen (WP2)
1.6	31.03.2020	Update	W. Rohm (IDM)
1.7	31.03.2020	Quality control	G. Józków (QM)
1.8	31.03.2020	Final check	M. Ilieva (PC)

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Abbreviations

A	AFM	Administration and Finance Manager
B	B2B	Business-to-Business (B2B)
C	CC BY-NC	Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial
	CRD	Station Coordinates file format
	CSA	Coordination and Support Action
	CSV	Comma-Separated Values text file format
D	DCC	Digital Curation Centre
	DI	Data and information related data
	DMP	Data Management Plan
	DOI	Digital Object Identifier
	DX.Y	Deliverable number X.Y (X – WP number, Y – deliverable number within WP)
E	EPN	EUREF Permanent Network
	EPOS-PL	European Plate Observing System – Poland
	ESA	European Space Agency
	EUREF	Regional Reference Frame Sub-Commission for Europe
F	FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability data principle
G	GA	General Assembly
	GATHERS	Integration of Geodetic and imAging TecHniques for monitoring and modelling the Earth's surface defoRmations and Seismic risk
	GDrive	Google Drive
	GDRP	General Data Protection Regulation
	GeoTIFF	Georeferenced Tagged Image File Format
	GIG	Główny Instytut Górnictwa (in Polish) for Central Mining Institute
	GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
H	H2020	Horizon 2020
I	IC	Internal communication documents

	IDM	Innovation and Data Manager
	IGf	Instytut Geofizyki Polskiej Akademii Nauk (in Polish) for Institute of Geophysics at Polish Academy of Sciences
	IGiG	Instytut Geodezji i Geoinformatyki (in Polish) for Institute of Geodesy and Geoinformatics
	IGRS	Integrated Geodetic Reference Stations
	IGS	International GNSS Service
	InSAR	Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar
	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
L	LAS	LASer file format
	LAZ	compressed laser file format
	LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
M	M3G	Multiple GNSS Networks
	MST	Management Support Team
O	OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
P	PD	Project Deliverables
	PDD	Project Deliverables Derivatives
	PhD	Philosophiae Doctor (in Latin) for postgraduate doctoral degree
	PMs	Personal Months
	PSD	Personal Specific Data
	PU	Public level of dissemination
Q	QM	Quality Manager
R	RE	External communication documents
	RINEX	Receiver Independent Exchange Format
S	Sapienza	Università Degli Studi Di Roma La Sapienza (in Italian) for Sapienza University of Rome
	SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar

	SLC	Single Look Complex format
T	TM	Technical Manager
	TUD	Technische Universiteit Delft (in Dutch) for Delft University of Technology
	TUW	Technische Universität Wien (in German) for Vienna University of Technology
U	UPWr	Uniwersytet Przyrodniczy we Wrocławiu (in Polish) for Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences
W	WP	Work Package

Executive summary

GATHERS is a networking project within the frame of Horizon 2020's Coordination and Support Action (CSA) TWINNING initiative, which is realised in the domain of the Earth sciences using following observation techniques: Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR). Three major aspects are discussed in the document: 1) storing and processing large amounts of observations and products, 2) sharing and accessing the products internally and externally, regarding the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), 3) managing project documentation – internal and external, as well as project deliverables.

Total amount of data, not exceeding 5TB, are going to be stored, as the project will mostly rely on data re-used from EPOS-PL project and obtained from industrial and research partners (IGf, GIG, ICEYE). Data that are available for GATHERS consortium: Project Deliverables (PD) and Internal Communication Documents (IC) will be stored in EMDesk and GDrive shared among Management Support Team (MST). Whereas, data that are potentially subject to exploitation or dissemination will be stored in the Zenodo repository. Each data set from the last group will obtain a Digital Object Identifier. Following data formats were identified: RINEX, CRD, LAS, LAZ, GeoTIFF, CSV. All are supported by Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), including metadata except RINEX. RINEX format requires a separate metadata definition which is provided by Metadata Management and distribution system for Multiple GNSS Networks (M3G). All data are interoperable and potentially used by open processing software.

Two modes of data sharing will be adopted: open/embargoed or restricted/closed, depending on the agreements with data providers, publication strategy and decision of the General Assembly whether results will be protected and exploited or disseminated. Innovation and Data Manager will grant access to restricted data. Proposed licences for data use is Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial (CC BY-NC).

Data Management Plan is a living document undergoing periodic updates prepared following "FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020".

1 Introduction

GATHERS is a networking project within the frame of Horizon 2020's Coordination and Support Action (CSA) TWINNING initiative, which will be realised in the domain of the Earth sciences. The project comprises knowledge and competences exchange between the Project Coordinator – Uniwersytet Przyrodniczy we Wrocławiu (UPWr) and internationally-leading research institutions as project's Partners in three advanced scientific disciplines. The Partners in this project are: 1) Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD) in Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) technique; 2) Technische Universitaet Wien (TUW) in Light Detection And Ranging (LiDAR), and 3) Universita Degli Studi di Roma La Sapienza (Sapienza) in Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) seismology. The overall objective of the project is a further development of the geospatial sciences to enlarge the number of research-intensive sections at Institute of Geodesy and Geoinformatics (IGiG) at UPWr, to foster development of leaders (to form Lead Research Working Group in InSAR, LiDAR and GNSS seismology), finally to

establish strong networks with the best Universities in Europe to form competitive research applications in H2020.

There are three major aspects of data management related to the proper functionality of the project. On one hand, the usage of these three up-to-date engineering technologies generate large amounts of data, which requires a strategic plan of collecting, processing, and storing the technical data. Another specific expression of the data management is the sharing and accessing the products internally and externally, regarding the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) – background and foreground, of each Consortium Member. Also, a significance must be given to the project documentation – internal and external, as well as project deliverables.

The main purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to describe the management of the data flow within the project on different levels – from data collection, processing, generation and distribution between the Consortium Members, within the communication with the European commission, to dissemination actions targeted at the stakeholders.

The DMP will be updated during the entire life of the project and beyond, following the project's needs like newcomming data, changes in the Consortium Agreement, and the periodic reviews of the project.

2 Data summary

The data and solutions developed within this project will illustrate quantitatively and qualitatively the expected potential impact of the TWINNING exercise within the coordinating institution (and possibly at regional/national level) based on indicators like expected future publications in peer reviewed journals, collaboration agreements with businesses, intellectual property, new innovative products or services.

2.1 Data types

The following data types are envisaged within project lifecycle and beyond (for more details see Table 1):

Data and metadata (DI) to the LiDAR, GNSS and InSAR observations, processing settings and outputs, reference seismic observations, deformations from levelling and geodetic and geophysical observations, extraction plans and longwall progress, modelled deformations.

Project Deliverables (PD) which will collect all the relevant results of the Project itself. At the end of the project, Project Deliverables Derivatives (PDD), a library of the best practices, success stories and business cases useful for every stakeholder interested in stepping up in the research and creating new innovating geodetic products and services will be available. Making this information accessible will help other Universities and companies to innovate, facilitate and catalyse new applications.

External communication documents (RE): all the PU documents to communicate GATHERS project and its results, such as technology and business analysis, presentations, guidelines and manuals, articles, papers, newsletters etc.

Internal communication documents (IC): according to the Data Management Methodology (described in this DMP) and with the aim of keeping within all data generated during the project, mainly those related to communication among stakeholders such as agenda and minutes of meetings, emails, proceedings, etc.

Personal specific data (PSD): data collected during the hackathons, B2B meetings, summer school's registration procedures.

Table 1. Data type list managed during lifetime of a project, including observations, products, project deliverables

Data name	Origin	Format	Owner	Maximum size estimate	Potential user
SAR raw data	ESA, ICEYE, etc.	SLC	ESA, ICEYE, etc.	1TB	GATHERS Consortium
InSAR deformation map (DI)	EPOS-PL	GeoTIFF + ESRI layer (*.lyr) ArcGIS *.mdf	UPWr	1TB	science, industry
LiDAR point cloud (DI)	EPOS-PL	LAS, LAZ	UPWr	1TB	science, industry
GNSS high frequency observations and coordinates (DI)	EPOS-PL	RINEX, CRD, ASCII	UPWr	1TB	science, industry
Reference seismic (DI)	EPOS-PL	ASCII, Matlab (*.mat)	IGf	1GB	science, industry
Reference deformation (DI)	EPOS-PL	*.grd, *.xlsx	GIG	100 Mb	science, industry
Software, tools or instruments	GATHERS	-	GATHERS Consortium	-	science, industry
Project deliverables (PD)	GATHERS	PDF	GATHERS Consortium	250Mb	EC, GATHERS Consortium, General public
External Communication Documents (RE)	GATHERS	PDF	GATHERS Consortium	1GB	General public
Internal Communication Documents (IC)	GATHERS	PDF	GATHERS Consortium	250Mb	GATHERS Consortium
Personal Specific Data (PSD)	GATHERS	*.xlsx	GATHERS Consortium	50Mb	GATHERS Consortium

2.2 Data sources

As this TWINNING exercise belongs to the Coordinate and Support Action, most of the data that will be used to develop trainings, summer schools and hackathons, and they will be re-used from other projects. For example InSAR, LiDAR and GNSS data obtained in the frame of EPOS-PL (www.epos-pl.eu) project for selected mining areas and mining tremor events from Mining Upper Silesia Episode will be the prime source. The data will be used in the initial stage of research for Master and PhD Theses, and as one of the study cases for Summer School. We will also use data stored in publically available repositories with SAR images: (scihub.copernicus.eu) and GNSS data (epncb.oma.be; igs.org).

The data are collected by Consortium Partners, either specifically for this project or re-used from previous research endeavours:

- EPOS-PL collected by a Leader (UPWr)
- Data from the TU Delft Integrated Geodetic Reference Stations (IGRS)

The other source of data will be made available by extensive business and research contacts of the Consortium. Following the first Business-to-Business (B2B) meeting (5.12.2019) leading spatial and mining business companies, universities, and research institutions already expressed interest in collaboration, products use and data sharing (see Table 2).

Table 2. List of companies that intend to share data with GATHERS Consortium

Company	Data provision
Solitech	LiDAR
OPEGIEKA	LiDAR
Laser-3D	LiDAR
Institute of Geophysics Polish Academy of Science (IGf)	Reference seismic
Head Office of Geodesy and Cartography	GNSS
ICEYE	InSAR
Central Mining Institute (GIG)	Reference deformation

3 FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data re-used, used and generated by GATHERS consortium are divided into two categories:

1) Data that are available for GATHERS Consortium: Project Deliverables (PD) and Internal Communication Documents (IC) which are stored in EMDesk GATHERS repository and have the backup in a Google Drive folder shared among the Management Support Team (MST):

EMDesk: Documents;

GDrive: GATHERS\DOCUMENTS_REPOSITORY;

2) Data that are potentially subject to exploitation (Grant Agreement Article 27.1) or dissemination (Grant Agreement 29.1), will be stored in the Zenodo repository. The following data types are considered:

Research publications (Grant Agreement Article 29.2) (RE);

Research data (Grant Agreement Article 29.3) (RE);

Software (tools) (Grant Agreement Article 29.3) (RE);

All PU marked Project Deliverables (PD).

All data will have an unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI), so the discussed results are replicable and traceable. Moreover, each data pack, divided into specific cases will have separate DOI and will be accessible with full metadata information. Naming convention adopted in GATHERS consortium data is related to the specific format (see Table 3) in use.

Table 3. List of data formats and naming conventions

Data format	Sensor	Name	Extension
RINEX	GNSS	SSSSDOYE SSSS - station 4 characters abbreviation, DOY - day of the year in GPS time E - session number	YYd YY - two digits d - observations file
CRD	GNSS	OOOWWWWD OOO - solution abbreviation WWWW - GPS week D - day of the GPS week	CRD
GeoTiff	SAR	OYYYYMMDD_YYYYMMDD_ppp O - orbit type (A for ascending, D for Descending, YYYYMMDD - YYYY for year, MM for month, DD for day for the beginning (first date) and the end (second date) of the monitored time span, ppp - product type: def for deformation map, coh for coherence map	tif
LAS, LAZ	LiDAR	Type_YYYYMMDD_SiteName Type - type if the point cloud origin: ALS for Airborne Laser Scanning, ULS for UAV-borne	las, laz

		Laser Scanning, TLS for Terrestrial Laser Scanning, DIM for Dense Image Matching, OTR for other point clouds, created by other sensors (non LiDAR or image matching point cloud, e.g. total station) YYYY - Year, MM - Month, DD - Day of data acquisition SiteName - short name describing site for which data was collected	
Reference seismic (DI)	Seismograph	PL.XXXX..AAA.NNNNNN PL - network code, XXXX - station code, AAA - location ID, NNNNNN - quality indicator	ASCII
Reference deformation (DI)	Levelling, modelling	YYYYMMDD_YYYYMMDD for levelling: YYYYMMDD - YYYY for year, MM for month, DD for day for the beginning (first date) and the end (second date) of the monitored time span; w_YYYYMMDD for modelling: w-subsidence, YYYYMMDD - YYYY for year, MM for month, DD for the last date of the monitored time span;	xlsx grd
Project deliverables (PD)	-	GATHERS-DX.Y-Description-Dissemination level-Version Full description available in D1.2 (section 6.2.2.).	pdf
External Communication Documents (RE)	-	GATHERS-RE-Description-Dissemination level-Version Full description available in D1.2 (section 6.2.2.).	pdf
Internal Communication Documents (IC)	-	GATHERS-MM-Description-Dissemination level-Version] GATHERS-IRE-Description-Dissemination level-Version] GATHERS-TX.Y-Description-Dissemination level-Version] Full description available in D1.2 (section 6.2.2.).	pdf

In order to improve findability of the data, following keywords (non-exhausting list provided) will be assigned to specific data sets and publications: GATHERS, name_of_the_case, start_date_of_the_case, end_date_of_the_case, InSAR, high-frequency GNSS observations, mining deformations, mining

tremors, induced seismicity, LiDAR. The project imposes a clear version naming convention for files, using naming and header information (RINEX, LAS). Whereas, the version management for GATHERS project documents will follow the full description available in section 6.2.2. of D1.2. Repository will store metadata. InSAR and LiDAR data will follow the standards common in Earth Sciences, listed in Digital Curation Centre (DCC) of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC):

- GeoTiff (http://docs.opengeospatial.org/is/19-008r4/19-008r4.html#_geotiff),
- LAS (<https://www.asprs.org/divisions-committees/lidar-division/laser-las-file-format-exchange-activities>) and LAZ (<https://laszip.org>).

Whereas the GNSS metadata will be distributed using International GNSS Service (IGS) sitelog format (ftp://igs.org/pub/station/general/sitelog_instr.txt) or M3G (<https://gnss-metadata.eu>).

3.2 Making data openly accessible

The data accessibility is structured as follows: the Innovation Management Procedure (D6.8, 5.3) is executed and taking into account obligation to protect results (Grant Agreement, Article 27.1), considering ownership of results (Grant Agreement, Article 26.2; Consortium Agreement, Article 8.2). The results will be disseminated (Grant Agreement, Article 29.1, with further modifications following Consortium Agreement 8.4.2.1) after 15 days prior notice to Partners, with 7 days objection limit.

Following data dissemination type is foreseen:

- The processed data, for which openly available sources are used, will be openly available by default i.e.: deformation maps from Sentinel-1, GNSS CRD data for freely available EPN or IGS sites, peer-review publications, bibliography metadata, software metadata (OPEN ACCESS, or EMBARGOED ACCESS);
- The re-used data (GNSS, LiDAR), provided by EPOS-PL sponsored sensor (Table 1), will be available only under contractual statement of the use of research infrastructure agreement, released by the third quarter (Q3) of year 2021, and only to non-commercial partners free of charge (RESTRICTED or EMBARGOED ACCESS);
- Data, provided voluntarily by third-party institutions, e.g. GIG, mining industry (Table 2), will be made available, after a Data Sharing Agreement will be signed (RESTRICTED or CLOSED).

Partners according to Grant Agreement Article 24 decided in Consortium Agreement Attachment 1 to claim background IPR of their respective software and know-hows, therefore these data are not going to be made available publicly. Full list of background IPR is listed in D6.8 Section 5.1.

Data will be sent out to the repository. GATHERS consortium is adopting Zenodo for data sharing, all the data will be linked to the OpenAIRE directory of GATHERS project to allow fast, efficient and transparent access to the data. “Community” of “GATHERS” will be created within a repository, which will contain all the disseminated data curated in the project. It allows building up a strong interest in the project results not only by the scientific community but also by industry, catering data exchange and inspiring new products. Partners reserve the right to duplicate all or some data in their own repositories.

Following data repository types will be used by the Consortium:

- Publication – open access peer-reviewed publications, made either available by publisher, or as a preprint, these will be deposited at the time of publication;
- Poster – following attendance to the conference, workshop, summer school or hackathon, deposited after event, publication will be made not later than 21 days after (if marked RE);
- Presentation – following attendance to the conference, workshop, summer school or hackathon, deposited after event, publication will be made not later than 21 days after (if marked RE);
- Dataset – it will be either deposited alongside with publication or as a separate stand-alone document, publishing time and conditions will depend on the data access agreement;
- Software – algorithms developed within this project during hackathons and trainings (Foreground IPR), and codified as a data processing tools, will be made available on the repository, providing that (Procedure for Innovation Management D6.8), General Assembly will make decision that it won't be protected and exploited.

Following rules will be imposed on the use of data stored at Zenodo repository by GATHERS consortium depending on the access level:

- Open Access / Embargoed Access – using GATHERS generated data, the user agrees to accept the product as it is, and also acknowledges that the GATHERS Consortium makes no assurances, implied or otherwise, for the accuracy or availability of the Product. The User shall indemnify, defend and hold the GATHERS Consortium and its affiliates harmless from any loss or damage resulting from any claim by any person relating to the data services provided under this agreement;
- Restricted – the access will be granted after account verification, following information will be collected: first and last name, email address, company, intended data use, declaration of non-commercial use, the access will be granted by IDM, no machine readable license will be provided. The data will be provided if not specified otherwise by separate license as for Open Access / Embargoed Access as it is.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data provided in Open Access are in formats that are made mostly available in format that are OGC standards (RINEX, LAS, GeoTIFF), therefore interoperable with major processing software:

- SLC (SAR) – Doris, SNAP, Gamma, SARscape
- LAS (LiDAR) – OPALS, LAStools, CloudCompare, FugroViewer, ArcGIS, PDAL
- RINEX (GNSS) – Bernese 5.2.GNSS Software, RTKLib, GAMIT
- GeoTIFF (all) – QGIS, ArcGIS

3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

For open data category the licences CC BY-NC will be adopted, which allow to share the data in any format and medium under the following terms: (BY) attribution (giving credits), (NC) non-commercial

use. However, other licenses will be considered: by introducing ND - non derivative, SA - share alike or revoking the NC component for selected datasets.

Data re-use is principle lead to shorten the embargo time to maximum 6 months for dataset published alongside with publication (Grant Agreement 29.2) and for stand-alone data embargo will be set on a case base. After the project completion date the data that were collected by the consortium, and were not protected and exploited will be made available to the public. This does not apply to third party data and project industrial partners that might seek other agreement for data release.

Data quality measures will be adopted from re-used data sets as provided by source project and partners.

4 Allocation of resources

Costs for making data FAIR in GATHERS are those allocated to “other direct costs” as well “personnel costs” (Innovation and Data Manager PMs). The budget for the maintenance is 25 000 €, and its allocation is fairly balanced between Leader from Widening Country (UPWr – 58%) and Consortium Partners (13% each).

The person responsible for coordinating GATHER's data management and access process is the Innovation and Data Manager, while the General Assembly will be the ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium and responsible for taking major strategic decisions with respect to data exploitation if reasonable. It will also promote consensus in case of conflict and, if no consensus can be found, it will take decisions according to the procedures and rules defined in the Consortium Agreement.

5 Data security

Data that are available for GATHERS consortium only (PD and IC), which are stored in the Google Drive folder – DOCUMENT_REPOSITORY, have access only by Management Support Team. Copy of these deliverables are also send to EMDesk cloud, where every Partner has access to by appointed responsible person. All is password protected and requires https connection.

Data for sharing are deposited on the Zenodo repository, password protected, with https protocol, access to upload into “Community” will be granted only for registered users by IDM, access to restricted datasets will be granted by IDM. Dataset will be managed by IDM.

In the event Personal Specific Data (PSD) is processed as the term is defined in the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (the “GDPR”) in the framework of GATHERS project the Partners undertake to respect their obligations in application of regulations in force and, especially, GDPR.

6 Ethical aspects

All participants of summer schools, B2B meetings, hackathons, trainings, workshops are providing informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data.

Anonymity and confidentiality: The basic and common principles valid for all research methods and all subjects involved will be providing participants strong assurances of anonymity and confidentiality and guaranteeing that participants will never be identifiable from the information they personally offer, except when the identification of the subject is necessary in relation to the activity and/or proposes of the research. In this case the content of the information to be provided to the participants and of the informed consent will specify this situation, in particular the proposes of this data processing and the period for which the personal data will be stored without anonymization, according to the principles and security measures of Regulation (UE) 2016/679 – GDPR.

Moreover, participants are informed that researchers shall protect them when publishing findings and during the conduct of the research itself. All records, leaflets, minutes, data captured online, recordings shall be treated with the strictest confidentiality. Names are changed in verbal transcripts of interviews, and details that might make the participants identifiable, are altered in such a way that participants do not become identifiable. Data will be stored securely.

Protection of personal data: Any data collection with human subjects will comply with the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon 2020, regardless of the country in which the research is carried out. Any survey focus group and/or formal interviews (all currently not planned) will be designed and conducted in accordance with the procedures defined by the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. A fundamental principle underpinning the whole research activity is respect for the welfare (health and safety) of the participants who take part in the work, and this principle will over-ride all other considerations when the work is executed. Other principles are: 1) participation only after informed consent, 2) privacy personal data protection, anonymity and confidentiality, 3) fairness, 4) equity, 5) justice, 6) social responsibility.

7 Other

The guideline document “FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020” has been used for the development of GATHERS Data Management Plan.

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